
**TRAWLING BAN IN THE GULF OF CASTELLAMMARE:
EFFECTS ON THE SMALL-SCALE FISHERY ECONOMICS
AND ON THE ABUNDANCE OF FISH**

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ABSTRACT

The present study intends to update a previous study (EC MED92/011) in order to (i) assess the effect of an eight-year trawl ban on the demersal resources (over trawlable and non-trawlable bottoms) in the Gulf of Castellammare, and (ii) investigate how these resources are now being exploited by the small-scale fishery, as well as the extent of any social or economic gain arising as a result of the trawl ban. The study is made of two parts: A) biological section, and B) socio-economic section.

A - Biological section

Four seasonal trawl surveys were carried out from June 1998 to March 1999 on the continental shelf. The stratum that yielded the highest CPUE was stratum A (10-50 m: 61248 gr/haul), followed by str. B (51-100 m: 47914 gr/haul) and str. C (101-200 m: 26356 gr/haul). Considering the seasons, CPUEs were 34663 gr/haul in spring, 52234 in summer, 53079 in autumn and 27578 in winter. *Mullus barbatus* was the most abundant species overall. Highly commercial species were the dominant category in almost all the seasons and strata, with a peak in str. A in summer.

Twelve trammel-gillnet surveys were carried out on a monthly basis in shallow waters on sandy bottoms (SB), rocky bottoms (RB) and an artificial reef area (ARA), from June 1998 to May 1999. The area that yielded the highest CPUE was SB (4000 gr/trip), followed by RB (3646 gr/trip) and ARA (3322 gr/trip). Considering the seasons, CPUEs were 2709 gr/trip in spring, 3569 in summer, 3168 in autumn and 4006 in winter. The most abundant species overall was *Boops boops*. Moderately commercial species dominated the trammel-gillnet catches; highly commercial species reached a peak in abundance in RB in summer.

The CPUEs of the total catch in the trawl surveys was larger in 1998-99 than in 1993-94, especially in str. A. Considering the single strata and seasons, CPUEs were larger in 1993-94 only in winter (str. B, C and total area) and in spring (stratum B). The CPUEs of the following target species (mean over the total area) decreased in 1998-99: *M. barbatus* (which increased in str. A), *Lithognathus mormyrus*, *Sepia officinalis*, *Eledone moschata*. The proportion of highly- and non-commercial species decreased in 1998-99, while that of moderately commercial species increased.

The CPUEs of the trammel-gillnet surveys were larger in 1998-99 than in 1993-94, especially in SB. Considering the single areas and seasons, there was a decrease in 1998-99 in spring (in ARA and RB). The CPUEs of following species decreased in 1998-99: *Octopus vulgaris* in RB, *Scorpaena porcus* in RB, *S. officinalis* in ARA and RB. The proportion of highly commercial species decreased in 1998-99, while that of moderately commercial species increased.

A landings survey of the small-scale fishery catches was carried out on a fortnightly basis from July 1998 to June 1999. The highest catches of the set net fishery were made in winter and spring, the lowest in summer. Fishermen in Castellammare and Balestrate obtained the largest CPUEs. Considering the Balestrate FAD fishery, dolphin fish (which is the target species) was the most abundant fish, followed by amberjack and juvenile bluefin tuna.

B - Socio-economic section

In 1998-99 there were 147 fishing vessels registered to fish in the Gulf of Castellammare. Of these, 96 were registered artisanal fishing boats. The main gear used by fishermen was a set net (trammel or gillnet). The economic assessment of the small-scale fishery required primary data, which were collected through a landings survey, a fishing characteristics survey and a motivations survey. The assessment of the financial performance of artisanal fishermen also data on fish price and capital costs were collected.

Net financial profit (boat income) of trammel netters in 1998-99 averaged 8.7 million lira (= 4493 Euro). Just fewer than 7% of operators incurred losses, while some 13% earned profits in excess of 25 million lira (= 12911 Euro). The fishery has the potential to be economically sustainable, since the capital necessary for its long-term continuation would be expected to earn a competitive return.

Biological data based on experimental trawl surveys and trammel net surveys showed a large increase in demersal stocks since the ban was imposed. However, over the period species composition has changed, with most of the biomass increase being for varieties classed as only

'moderately commercial'. This may therefore have attenuated the financial gains for artisanal fishermen.

Recreational fishing was identified as the single most important problem facing professional artisanal fishermen. As far as the ban is concerned, most fishermen felt that fishing was "better" or "much better" since the ban, 14% "worse" or "much worse". This contrasts with their view of prospects, where 24% believed fishing would be "better" or "much better" while 55% stated it would be "worse" or "much worse". Despite their apparent pessimism, the overwhelming majority (86%) signalled their intention of carrying on fishing in the Gulf in the future.

SUMMARY FOR NON-SPECIALISTS

The Gulf of Castellammare (NW Sicily, Mediterranean Sea) was the location of an important management measure in 1990, which is still in place: a year round trawling ban. This measure aimed at rebuilding the depleted demersal stocks. A study (MED92/011) co-funded by EC DGXIV was carried out by I.R.M.A. (formerly: I.T.P.P.) in 1993-95: that study highlighted the dramatic increase of demersal resources four years after the ban, compared to data collected two years before the ban.

The trawling ban also has helped to give the small-scale fishermen the chance of fishing in much safer conditions on a much more abundant resource. The present study had two main objectives:

- i) to update the data obtained in the previous study in order to establish whether the abundance of demersal fish stocks is still increasing and whether the fish assemblage composition and structure have further changed. This was achieved through fishing surveys aimed at assessing the current state of resources;
- ii) to investigate how these resources are now being exploited by the small-scale fishery (which now dominates the fishing sector in the Gulf of Castellammare), and the extent of any social or economic gain arising as a result of the trawling ban. This was achieved through interviews and data collection at landings, aimed at assessing the amount of catches and at investigating both the fishing habits of artisanal fishermen and their attitude towards the trawling ban and towards possible changes in the management regime.

This report is thus made of two parts: **(A)** a biological section made by IRMA – Laboratory of Marine Biology of Castellammare del Golfo (Italy); **(B)** a socio-economic section, including a legislative appendix, made by CEMARE – University of Portsmouth (Great Britain).

A - Biological section

METHODOLOGIES

Trawlable area

Four trawl surveys were carried out seasonally from June 1998 to March 1999, for a total of 105 30-min hauls. The study area extended from the shallowest bottoms compatible with trawling as far as the –200 m isobath, and was divided in three strata: A (10-50 m), B (51-100 m) and C (101-200 m). A commercial trawler was hired for the sampling operations. Yields were expressed as CPUEs (catch per unit effort) in gr/haul. The abundance of target species at sea was expressed as density in the study area (kg/km^2). The species caught were grouped in three commercial categories, based on their market price: highly commercial (h.c.), moderately commercial (m.c.) and non-commercial (n.c.). The size structure of twelve target species was presented in the form of bar charts and discussed. The fish assemblage was analysed in terms of species richness and biological diversity, and multifactorial analyses were performed on the 1993-94 and 1998-99 data, to investigate possible changes in the community structure.

Non-trawlable area

Twelve trammel-gillnet surveys were made in the following three areas (each including two stations) from June 1998 to May 1999: RB (rocky bottom), ARA (artificial reef area) and SB (sandy bottom), for a total of 72 samplings. CPUEs were expressed in gr/500 m net/12 hrs fishing time. The fish assemblage was analysed in terms of species richness and biological diversity.

Effect of the trawl ban

The effect of the trawl ban eight years after its start was estimated through a comparison with the data of MED92/011.